

PYRIDINE COMPLEXES OF METALLIC PERCHLORATES. PART III.
COMPOSITION AND STABILITY OF COPPER PYRIDINE
PERCHLORATES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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An attempt has been made to determine the nature and stability of the complexes, which are formed when an aqueous solution of copper perchlorate is treated with pyridine, by measurement of the distribution coefficients of varying quantities of pyridine between benzene and a *N*/10-aqueous solution of copper perchlorate. The results seem to indicate that only two complexes are formed containing respectively 2 and 4 molecules of pyridine per atom of copper.

The preparation and general properties of pyridine complexes of some metallic perchlorates have been described in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 33). From measurements of dissociation pressures of copper pyridine perchlorates at different temperatures and isothermals (pressure-composition curves at definite temperatures) it has been found that in the solid phase only two complexes, *e.g.*, $\text{CuPy}_4(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{CuPy}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ exist. It is well known that amines of anhydrous salts vary considerably in stability, and may be roughly divided into two classes, *viz.*, (a) those stable in aqueous solution and (b) those decomposed by water. It was therefore considered worthwhile to investigate the nature of the complexes formed by metallic perchlorates with pyridine in aqueous solution.

By using the spectrophotometric method Job (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 185) determined the nature of the complexes which copper sulphate formed with ammonia and ethylenediamine and found that both these bases formed complexes containing four molecules of the base per one atom of copper of the type of Schweitzer's salt. With the help of the same method Aumras and Tamisier (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1933, 53, 102) studied the complex formation between copper nitrate and methylamine, allylamine, pyridine and other nitrogenous organic bases. They found that pyridine gave with copper nitrate a complex analogous to that formed with ammonia, but much more dissociated. The complex is no doubt formed through the nitrogen atom, but the work of Aumras and Tamisier (*loc. cit.*) shows that although the nitrogen of the pyridine nucleus react, the nitrogen of the pentagonal nucleus is inactive with respect to the copper salt.

One way of determining the complexity of a solute in an aqueous solution is by means of the partition coefficient method. According to Nernst's distribution law, the concentration of a substance in two immiscible solvents, in equilibrium, bear a constant ratio to each other provided the molecular weight is the same in both the solvents; or, inverting the law, any deviation from the constant concentration ratio will serve as a measure of any molecular change which the distributing substance undergoes in the different solvents as pointed out by Hantz and Sebaldt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 258). Dawson and McCrac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 1239) as also Tamisier (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1933, 53, 157) have utilized these facts for investigating the nature of the amines of copper, zinc and cadmium, using water and chloroform as two immiscible liquids.

In the present investigations, water and benzene have been chosen as the immiscible solvents, since chloroform is much more volatile than benzene at the temperature of the experiments. The working temperature was selected to be 35°, as the temperature of the laboratory was above 30° for major part of the year. Hantz and Sebaldt (*loc. cit.*)

have shown that the ratio of the concentrations of pyridine in benzene and water for different concentrations of pyridine is constant and independent of the initial concentration of pyridine; thus it can be safely concluded that the molecular complexity of pyridine in benzene and water is the same.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solution of the salt was prepared by taking a known volume (2.5 c.c.) of 2 *N*-copper perchlorate solution and to this varying volumes of 2*N*-pyridine solution were added. The mixture was made up to 50 c.c. with water so that the solution was *N*/10 with respect to copper perchlorate. These solutions were then poured into a number of glass-stoppered separating funnels which had been tested free from leakage. Benzene (50 c.c.) was added to each and the funnels were shaken in a thermostat maintained at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ until equilibrium was established. The aqueous and benzene layers were allowed to separate in the thermostat and the layers were withdrawn quickly. The pyridine content of each layer was estimated separately. For the estimation of pyridine in the benzene layer, 40 c.c. of the liquid were taken in a glass-stoppered bottle, a drop of methyl orange and about 50 c.c. of water added, and the pyridine titrated with *N*-HCl until a permanent pink colour was obtained. For the estimation of pyridine in the aqueous layer, 40 c.c. of the solution was transferred to a round-bottomed flask, fitted with a rubber stopper having two holes, one of which carried a tube connected with a boiler for steam and to the other was attached an alkali trap and a condenser. Excess of concentrated sodium hydroxide solution was added to the flask and the whole of the pyridine was distilled into a bottle containing 25 c.c. of *N*-acid solution. The excess of the acid in the bottle was then titrated with seminormal sodium hydroxide solution. The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

M.L. ratio Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : total pyridine.	Distribution coeff of Py in water/ Py. in benzene.	*Conc. of pyridine in benzene.	*Total conc. of pyridine in water.	*Conc. of "free" pyridine.	*Conc. of "con- bined" pyridine.	No. of mols. of pyridine com- bined per atom of copper.	$K_1 \times 10^4$.	$K_2 \times 10^8$
(a)	(d)	(b)	(w)	(f)	(e)	(r)	...	...
1:10	0.639	0.3950	0.1940	0.1046	0.0904	1.808	1.45	...
1:12	0.628	0.3686	0.2314	0.1264	0.1050	2.100	2.31	30.4
1:14	0.610	0.4348	0.2652	0.1491	0.1161	2.322	3.57	11.2
1:15	0.603	0.4679	0.2821	0.1604	0.1217	2.435	4.26	9.3
1:16	0.594	0.5018	0.2932	0.1721	0.1261	2.522	5.14	8.4
1:17	0.591	0.5342	0.3158	0.1832	0.1326	2.652	5.73	6.9
1:18	0.585	0.5672	0.3328	0.1945	0.1383	2.766	6.39	6.1
1:20	0.579	0.6323	0.3677	0.2169	0.1508	3.016	7.22	4.6
1:22	0.568	0.7015	0.3985	0.2406	0.1579	3.158	8.94	4.2
1:24	0.560	0.7693	0.4307	0.2638	0.1669	3.338	9.60	3.4
1:26	0.550	0.8377	0.4623	0.2874	0.1749	3.498	9.78	2.6
1:28	0.543	0.9082	0.4918	0.3116	0.1802	3.604	10.35	2.4
1:30	0.535	0.9793	0.5207	0.3359	0.1848	3.696	10.48	2.0

* in g. mol./litre

DISCUSSION

The values in column (a) are calculated from the quantities of copper perchlorate and pyridine actually present in the solutions. The distribution coefficient values are obtained by plotting the results of Hantz and Sebaldt (*loc. cit.*) and the values for 35° are determined from the curve. The figures in columns (b) and (w) are obtained from the results of experiments. From a knowledge of the distribution coefficient in pure water and benzene, it is possible to calculate the concentration of pyridine in aqueous solution which is in equilibrium with any particular concentration of pyridine in benzene. This quantity may be regarded as "free" pyridine shown in column (f). The difference between the total pyridine (w) and the "free" pyridine (f) gives the amount of pyridine which is in combination of the copper salt and these values are tabulated in column (c). Hence, it is possible to calculate the number of molecules of pyridine which is in combination with one atom of copper in the salt solution and these values are shown in column (r).

The calculation of equilibrium constants K_1 and K_2 depends upon the application of the law of mass action. This law can be applied only when the constitution of the complexes formed in the solution phase is known. As it is precisely the question of determining this constitution, which is under consideration, it is necessary to make *a priori* assumptions regarding the complexes formed and to retain those which correspond to the experimental results. Dawson and McCrae (*loc. cit.*) have found that the tetrammine complex of copper dissociates into the diammine complex. As pyridine complexes are analogous to the amines, it may be assumed that the highest pyridine complex formed in solution is the tetrapyridine complex which may dissociate in either of the two ways shown below:—

where Py stands for a molecule of pyridine, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$.

On the basis of the above hypothesis,

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{Cu}^{++}][\text{Py}]^4}{[\text{CuPy}_4^{++}]} \text{ and } K_2 = \frac{[\text{CuPy}_2^{++}][\text{Py}]^2}{[\text{CuPy}_4^{++}]}$$

If r is the number of molecules of pyridine which are in combination with an atom of copper, it can be shown that

$$K_1 = \frac{4-r}{r} [\text{Py}]^4 \text{ and } K_2 = \frac{4-r}{r-2} [\text{Py}]^2$$

The average value for K_1 obtained for copper perchlorate and pyridine is 6.5×10^{-4} which is of the same order as the value 3.1×10^{-4} found by Auméras and Tamisier (*loc. cit.*) for copper nitrate and pyridine.

The divergence in the values of K_1 and K_2 is not surprising, because the co-ordination number of a metal, like copper, is not necessarily invariable on account of the fact that in solution more than one complex are in a state of mobile equilibrium. The invariability of the co-ordination number can be considered as a result of the chemical

forces and the nature of the atoms taking part in the formation of the complex. It is not the case with copper perchlorate solution which can only form complexes by means of very mobile equilibrium corresponding to the maximum stability of the dissolved systems. It is therefore probable that a pyridine solution of copper perchlorate in water contains several complexes capable of formation according to Werner's theory, these complexes being in equilibrium with one another. When the concentrations of pyridine are changed, however, it is possible to arrive at zones of concentration where one of the complexes exists alone to the exclusion of the other, or, at least formed in the greatest proportion in comparison with the others.

Two such zones become apparent when one examines the values of τ , the number of molecules of pyridine in combination with an atom of copper. It appears that a higher and a lower pyridinated complexes are present in the solutions in mobile equilibrium with one another. The regular and steady increase and decrease respectively in the values of K_1 and K_2 seem to indicate that the higher pyridinated complex in solution dissociates progressively and rapidly into the lower pyridinated complex with the decrease in the concentration of pyridine in solution, or, in other words, the higher pyridinated complex is stable in solution only when a large excess of pyridine is present, but at low concentrations of pyridine the lower pyridinated complex is more stable. It can therefore be deduced from the results of the experiments that, in the interval of the concentrations of pyridine studied, the aqueous solution of copper perchlorate does not form several complexes but only two which contain 2 and 4 molecules of pyridine per atom of copper, especially in view of the fact that these are the complexes which exist in the solid phase.

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